

Utilizing Hybrid P4 Solutions to Enhance 5G gNB with Data Plane Programmability

Mohsen Memarian*, Andreas Kassler*[†], Karl-Johan Grinnemo*, Sándor Laki[‡], Gergely Pongracz[§], Johan Forsman[¶]

*Computer Science Department, Karlstad University, Karlstad, Sweden

[†]Institute of Applied Computer Science, Deggendorf Institute of Technology, Deggendorf, Germany

[‡]Faculty of Informatics, ELTE Eötvös Loránd University, Budapest, Hungary

[§]Ericsson Research, Budapest, Hungary

[¶]TietoEvry, Umeå, Sweden

Email: *mohsen.memarian@kau.se, andreas.kassler@kau.se, karlgrin@kau.se [†]andreas.kassler@th-deg.de,

[‡]lakis@inf.elte.hu, [§]gergely.pongracz@ericsson.com, [¶]johan.forsman@tietoevry.com

Abstract—The typical approach to data plane programming involves deploying a single P4 program to a single target. However, different targets have different capabilities, functionalities, and support for various programming languages apart from P4. Consequently, disaggregating a single data plane program into multiple subprograms that run on different targets can take advantage of the strengths of each target, which is particularly important in the context of 5G, as certain data plane processing functions, like buffering and retransmission for RLC processing, cannot effectively be expressed in P4. This paper explores the disaggregation of a 5G gNB across a P4-programmable SmartNIC and an x86 server using DPDK-based processing, leveraging the strengths of each target. We assess the performance of our hybrid approach by varying which parts of the pipeline run on the SmartNIC and the x86, as well as the number of cores allocated on the host for the non-P4 part of the pipeline.

Index Terms—5G gNB, P4, Data Plane, SmartNIC

I. INTRODUCTION

Data plane disaggregation leverages the specific strengths of various packet processing hardware to meet network requirements by distributing functionalities among them. By breaking down packet processing pipelines into separate components, some can be deployed on x86 servers, taking advantage of their abundant resources, while others can be accelerated using SmartNICs, FPGAs, or switch ASICs. Recent advancements in network programmability with the P4 language have enabled flexible, protocol-independent control over packet processing on reprogrammable hardware. P4 programs can be compiled for different hardware targets, including SmartNICs, switch ASICs, and even x86 DPDK code. SmartNICs are especially effective at offloading network functions to and from x86 servers, enhancing efficiency and reducing the processing load.

In 5G/6G networks, disaggregating data plane programs is essential for efficiently managing diverse traffic patterns and optimizing latency, throughput, and resource utilization [1]. For instance, within the gNodeB (gNB) context, certain data plane functions can be executed on P4 programmable devices, such as encapsulating and decapsulating GTP-U packets and mapping QoS flows to Radio Bearers (RBs) in the Service Data Adaptation Protocol (SDAP). However, the P4 language's

expressiveness is significantly limited, making it challenging to describe complex packet processing operations such as loops, packet buffering, or cryptography on P4 programmable hardware targets. Consequently, the essential functions of gNB, like buffering and retransmission in the Radio Link Control (RLC) layer and header compression and encryption in the Packet Data Convergence Protocol (PDCP) layer, cannot be effectively implemented using P4. Therefore, the gNB's packet processing pipeline must be disaggregated, with some parts offloaded to P4 programmable devices while others require alternative solutions.

Several previous approaches have focused on the UPF and its acceleration with P4. MacDavid [2] developed a P4-UPF on Tofino, resulting in a high-performance UPF that optimizes throughput and latency. However, Tofino handles all processing, including GTP handling. To ease the load on Tofino's limited resources, x86 can manage inactive users' traffic. Bose *et al.* [3] investigated programmable data planes for high-performance UPF, creating prototypes ranging from software-only DPDK-based versions to those offloading functions to programmable hardware. However, the UPF has a simple data plane that can be easily implemented in programmable hardware alone, and they don't consider this approach. Regarding gNB, Vörös *et al.* [4] suggested a hybrid gNB that combines Tofino with DPDK-based external services to manage complex functions such as retransmission. Singh *et al.* [5] introduced hybrid P4 pipelines for UPF and gNB, leveraging the capabilities of Tofino and x86 to improve throughput and latency, with Tofino handling most packet processing and DPDK managing unsupported functions. However, they don't leverage the capabilities of a SmartNIC, which we think will be more and more common in modern platforms. A SmartNIC can be up to 15x cheaper than a Tofino [6], [7]. Though SmartNICs have lower individual performance, we can scale the performance using multiple devices simultaneously.

In this paper, we propose a scalable hybrid solution for gNB data plane disaggregation by distributing packet processing functions between a P4-programmable SmartNIC and an x86 server. Our approach leverages the strengths of each

Fig. 1: Diagram of packet handling and offloading from SmartNIC to x86.

hardware target, utilizing the SmartNIC for low-latency packet processing, and the x86 server for handling more complex tasks that exceed the capabilities of P4, such as buffering. Our experimental evaluation revealed that while the SmartNIC is effective for certain tasks, it encounters a bottleneck when handling more complex gNB functions, particularly packet cloning, which led to a 40% reduction in throughput. By offloading some processing tasks to the x86 server, we were able to alleviate this bottleneck, increasing overall throughput by up to 50%, from 8.5 million packets per second (MPPS) on the SmartNIC alone to 12.75 MPPS with full offloading to the x86, due to the scalability of the DPDK performance as more CPU cores are allocated. These findings underscore that the decision to offload processing or keep it on the SmartNIC must be carefully balanced based on specific processing requirements and available hardware resources to achieve optimal performance in 5G gNB implementations.

II. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

Recent SmartNICs have programmable features that allow packet processing on the card. However, due to their limited resources and hardware processing capacities, resource-intensive functions may be better performed on the x86, which generally has more resources such as memory and CPU. The decision of whether packets should be processed on the SmartNIC or the x86 can be implemented by reading a packet marker on the SmartNIC. We can use flow specifications in a MAT to identify the corresponding DRB and determine which DRB entity should handle the processing. DRB is a logical channel that carries user plane data between the gNB and the User Equipment (UE).

In terms of modularity, each DRB may include entities on both the SmartNIC and the x86. The connection between DRB

entities is facilitated through Virtual Interfaces (VFs) provided by the SmartNIC. The SmartNIC we use in this study can support up to 64 VFs created from Physical Interfaces (PFs) via Single Root I/O Virtualization (SR-IOV), which share the resources of the PF while remaining isolated. When these VFs are assigned to DPDK applications on the x86, the applications can directly access the PCI device, bypassing the host kernel and ensuring low-latency packet forwarding.

In terms of process management, SmartNIC supports parallel packet processing, while DPDK APIs facilitate managing multithreaded applications on x86. In a multithreaded DPDK environment, components like hash tables and ring buffers can be configured to ensure safe simultaneous access. For example, DPDK allows ring buffers to be configured as multi-producer/multi-consumer, single-producer/single-consumer, or a combination of both. Also, instead of a single large DPDK app, processing can be split into smaller applications, allowing more flexibility in distributing CPU cores between various processes. The sub-apps can communicate with each other through ring buffers.

We focus on the design of the Central Unit (CU) and Distributed Unit (DU), which are key components of a 5G gNB, with the CU handling higher-layer protocols like GTP, SDAP, and PDCP, and the DU managing lower-layer protocols such as RLC layer. However, we envision utilizing an x86 server as a Radio Unit (RU) in this architecture, where it can transmit and receive radio signals over the air by running a UHD-DPDK application that pulls packets from the network interface and generates radio samples. UHD (USRP Hardware Driver) [8] is a framework designed for use with Ettus Research's Universal Software Radio Peripheral (USRP) devices [9], which are widely used in Software-Defined Radio

Fig. 2: Throughput comparison of SmartNIC gNB.p4 across various processing steps.

(SDR) applications. When combined with the DPDK, the system leverages DPDK’s high-speed data processing capabilities.

Figure 1 depicts the packet processing workflow. Upon the arrival of a packet at the SmartNIC, the location for processing is determined by reading a packet marker. Both the SmartNIC and the host follow a specific packet processing path: A 64 K-entry MAT/hash-table identifies the corresponding DRB entity based on flow attributes, such as the GTP Tunnel Endpoint Identifier (TEID). In the downlink path, GTP decapsulation occurs first, followed by adding SDAP, PDCP, and RLC headers. If buffering is enabled, the gNB app clones the packet and enqueues the cloned packet’s memory buffer (mbuf) address to a ring buffer. On the receiving end, the Buffering as a Service (BaaS) app as a secondary DPDK app dequeues the packet’s mbuf address from the same ring buffer. The BaaS app includes a hash table that keeps track of the memory addresses of packet copies until an acknowledgment is received or the timer expires, triggering retransmission to the x86 RU before being forwarded to the UE. In the uplink path, packets are categorized as either RLC acknowledgment or RLC data. RLC acknowledgment packets are directed to the buffering service app, while RLC data packets undergo RLC, PDCP, and SDAP header removal before GTP encapsulation and forwarding to the UPF.

III. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

A. Experiment Setup

Our evaluation setup consists of the Device Under Test (DUT), which features an Intel® Xeon® Silver 4114 CPU running at 2.20 GHz with 20 cores, 32 GB of DDR4 RAM, Ubuntu 20.04, and DPDK v.23.03. DUT is the node where the gNB network function is executed. It is equipped with a Netronome Agilio CX 2x40G SmartNIC featuring 60 processing cores called micro-engines, each clocked at 800 MHz, with eight hardware threads per core, 32 KB instruction memory, 4 KB data memory, and CRC acceleration, optimized for packet parallel processing. We use a separate x86 server as a traffic generator using Trex v.3.04, which connects directly with fiber to the DUT’s SmartNIC. We generate downlink traffic at a line

Fig. 3: Throughput comparison of the SmartNIC p4wire.p4 + x86 gNB.c across various processing steps.

rate of 40 Gbps, with a packet size of 128 bytes, and varying destination IP addresses to mimic 64k UEs. Trex measures throughput by sending packets to the DUT and monitoring the rate at which they are processed and returned without any drop. The confidence level is approximately $\pm 0.5\%$.

B. Baselines

In the evaluation section, we will compare our gNB implementation against two baseline setups:

1) *L2FWD.p4*: This is a simple P4 program developed for the SmartNIC. It receives packets from the PFs of the SmartNIC, swaps the source and destination MAC addresses, and then returns the packets to the PFs.

2) *P4Wire.p4 and L2FWD.c*: This setup consists of a P4Wire program on the SmartNIC and an L2 forwarding DPDK application on the x86 host. The P4Wire program receives packets from the PFs, uses a MAT to decide the egress VF based on the ingress PF, and then forwards the packets to the designated VF. The DPDK application receives packets from the VFs, swaps the source and destination MAC addresses, and then sends the packets back to the VFs. Finally, the P4Wire program returns the packets to the PFs.

C. Throughput Performance

First, we address the question of what is the maximum throughput achievable using a SmartNIC with a basic L2 forwarding program and how throughput changes as additional gNB operations are added to the SmartNIC. In Figure 2, we can observe the impact of incorporating more complex operations into the gNB pipeline on the processing power of the SmartNIC. We divide the gNB processing pipeline into distinct steps, each adding incremental operations to the SmartNIC, to evaluate their impact on throughput. Starting at Step 0, basic L2 forwarding with MAC Swapping (*L2FWD.p4*) establishes a baseline throughput of approximately 39 MPPS. With the addition of GTP decapsulation in Step 1, the throughput slightly decreases to around 35 MPPS. Moving to Step 2, appending and populating the SDAP, PDCP, and RLC headers leads to a further reduction in throughput

to about 20 MPPS. Step 3 introduces a 64 K-entry MAT, dropping the throughput to approximately 14 MPPS. In Step 4, cloning is performed on the SmartNIC, and the cloned packets are dropped immediately, the overall throughput decreases to roughly 9.60 MPPS. In Step 5, the cloned packets are sent to the x86 for buffering, as is necessary, the throughput reduces further to about 8.62 MPPS. Together, these two steps result in an overall throughput reduction of approximately 40%.

Second, we answer the question of how much throughput can the SmartNIC inject into the x86 DPDK user space, how throughput changes as additional gNB operations are added to the x86 DPDK application, and how performing cloning on a SmartNIC compared to doing it on an x86 host in terms of throughput and resource consumption. Figure 3 demonstrates how adding more complex operations to the gNB pipeline impacts the x86 processing power. We implemented a P4Wire program (P4Wire.p4) on the SmartNIC that forwards packets from PFs to VFs, reaching the x86 DPDK application directly without further on-card processing. In Step 0, we measure the maximum throughput the SmartNIC can inject into the x86, where the DPDK app receives and drops packets, achieving a rate of 32.5 MPPS. In Step 1, basic L2 forwarding with MAC swapping (L2FWD.c) reduces the throughput to around 23.95 MPPS. Step 2 introduces GTP decapsulation, slightly lowering the rate to 23 MPPS. In Step 3, adding and filling SDAP, PDCP, and RLC headers decreases throughput further to 21.5 MPPS. Step 4, which involves a 64K-entry hash table, drops it to 19.44 MPPS. Finally, in Step 5, cloning packets on the x86 and enqueueing them into ring buffers lead to a 35% reduction, bringing the throughput down to approximately 12.75 MPPS. Up to four CPU cores, the throughput increases at a steeper slope, but beyond that, the slope begins to flatten. This likely happens because, initially, the SmartNIC isn't a bottleneck, so adding more CPU cores significantly boosts throughput. However, after a certain point, the SmartNIC can't inject packets fast enough, so adding more CPU cores gives smaller gains. It's also important to note that, before the cloning step, the x86 gNB program experiences a smaller percentage drop in throughput compared to the SmartNIC gNB program, as illustrated in Figure 2. When analyzing the impact of packet cloning, Figure 3 (Step 5), shows that throughput on the x86 can decrease by up to 35% during cloning, while a similar operation on the SmartNIC results in a drop of 40%, as depicted in Figure 2 (Step 5). In the case of the SmartNIC, we consider the effect of directing cloned packets to VFs, while in the x86 case, we consider the effect of enqueueing cloned packets to ring buffers. In both scenarios, the goal is for the cloned packets to reach the BaaS application.

Third, we examine what is the impact on throughput when gNB packet processing is split between the SmartNIC and the x86. Figure 4 shows the overall throughput of the DUT based on the number of x86 CPU cores used. The graph indicates the effect of moving the gNB packet processing from the SmartNIC to the x86. We divide the packets into two groups based on a marker in the IPv4 Identification field, specifying their gNB processing target. The first group is processed

Fig. 4: Throughput vs. number of x86 CPU cores for different offloading ratios between SmartNIC gNB.p4 and x86 gNB.c.

on the SmartNIC, and the second on the x86, with both undergoing GTP, SDAP, PDCP, RLC, and MAT/hash-table processing. Initially, 100% of the packets are processed on the SmartNIC. Gradually, we adjust the proportions, reducing the first group and increasing the second, until 100% of the packets are processed on the x86, with the SmartNIC solely forwarding packets to the x86 for gNB processing. The SmartNIC achieves a maximum throughput of 14 MPPS independently, as indicated in Figure 2 (Step 3). As the amount of offloaded traffic increases, more x86 CPU cores are required to handle the traffic. With 100% offloading and 8 CPU cores, the throughput reaches 19.5 MPPS, as shown in Figure 3 (Step 4). Offloading results in a gradual increase in overall throughput as x86 cores assist in processing a portion of the traffic. The overall throughput consistently falls between the extreme scenarios of all gNB processing on the SmartNIC and all gNB processing on the x86.

In terms of scalability, As demonstrated in Figures 3 and 4, the throughput increases as the number of CPU cores increases, as long as the SmartNIC does not become a bottleneck. This increase is due to the multi-threaded architecture of DPDK applications, where threads work independently, and components like hash tables and ring buffers (cf. Figure 1) are designed to allow safe simultaneous access. It's important to ensure that the number of CPU cores is always less than or equal to the number of VF interfaces. If we intend to increase the number of CPU cores, we must also increase the number of VFs to avoid thread contention during packet pulling from interfaces.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work was carried out within the Data-driven Latency-sensitive Mobile Services for a Digitalized Society (DRIVE) project, which is partly funded by the Knowledge Foundation of Sweden. The research leading to these results has also received funding from the European Commission through the HORIZON 6G SNS JU DESIRE6G (G.A. 101096466).

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